

HUMAN POSE ESTIMATION USING COMPUTER VISION FOR TRACKING PATIENT'S MOVEMENT

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ABSTRACT:

Our project focuses on real-time human pose estimation using Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) for health care applications. We address limitations in existing technologies by not only tracking healthcare objects but also emphasizing human health concerns. Unlike systems that plot a single person in a frame, our approach utilizes computer vision for multi-recognition, enhancing rehabilitation and movement tracking for patients. Leveraging the Coco dataset and mediapipe, our system identifies key joints and edges, estimating the entire human pose.

We integrate technologies for drowsiness detection, utilizing the eye aspect ratio with dlib, and fall prevention, calculating normal motion angles. With a focus on exercise correctness and patient safety, the system provides real-time monitoring and issues alerts for potential injuries. Achieving an accuracy of 85.47%, our project aims to contribute to healthcare by addressing exercise tracking, drowsiness prevention, and fall detection for patient well-being.

KEYWORDS: Conventional healthcare, Dizziness detection, Fall detection, unobtrusive observation, CNN.

INTRODUCTION

Human pose estimation using computer vision has emerged as a transformative technology, revolutionizing the landscape of rehabilitation monitoring. This cutting-edge approach brings forth advanced capabilities in precisely tracking and analyzing body movements, ushering in an era of objective and non-invasive assessment of patients' progress while concurrently addressing concerns related to dizziness and fall prevention during rehabilitation.

Traditionally, rehabilitation monitoring heavily relied on subjective observations and self-reported data, often leading to limitations in accuracy and efficacy. However, the advent of computer vision algorithms has paved the way for real-time extraction of detailed information regarding the positions and orientations of a person's body parts. This revolutionary technology offers a paradigm shift by providing

objective and non-invasive assessments of body movements, thereby significantly enhancing the quality of patient care in rehabilitation settings.

The significance of human pose estimation technology in rehabilitation monitoring becomes evident in its ability to detect dizziness, a common symptom in various medical conditions. By continuously monitoring a patient's movements, computer vision systems can identify irregular postures indicative of dizziness, allowing for prompt intervention by healthcare professionals. This early detection capability is crucial for ensuring timely medical attention and tailored interventions.

Furthermore, human pose estimation plays a critical role in fall detection, particularly for individuals with mobility challenges. By employing algorithms that identify unstable postures, the technology can trigger alerts when a fall risk is detected, providing an additional layer of safety and reducing the likelihood of severe injuries. This aspect is particularly impactful in healthcare scenarios where patient safety is of utmost concern.

The integration of human pose estimation into rehabilitation monitoring not only enhances assessment accuracy but also facilitates the creation of personalized rehabilitation plans. The real-time, objective insights provided by this technology offer a dynamic approach to patient care, enabling healthcare professionals to tailor interventions based on precise movement data. This personalized approach contributes to improved outcomes and a higher quality of care for patients undergoing rehabilitation.

In the healthcare sector, human pose estimation technology holds immense promise, optimizing rehabilitation processes, tracking progress, and ensuring patient safety by promptly identifying dizziness and fall risk. By offering a comprehensive solution that goes beyond traditional methods, this technology addresses the evolving needs of healthcare providers and patients alike. Its potential to enhance the

overall quality of healthcare services positions it as a valuable tool for the future of rehabilitation monitoring.

The game-changing nature of human pose estimation in rehabilitation monitoring is evident in its reliable and precise means of assessing patient progress, detecting dizziness, and preventing falls. This transformative technology not only elevates the standards of rehabilitation care but also contributes to the broader improvement of healthcare services. While the specifics of the algorithms used in human pose estimation are not delved into in this context, it is worth noting that these typically involve sophisticated computer vision techniques, including Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) for pose estimation, keypoint detection, and tracking. As technology continues to evolve, the integration of human pose estimation in healthcare settings holds the potential to redefine the future of rehabilitation monitoring, offering enhanced patient-centric care and improved overall health outcomes.

ARCHITECTURE DIAGRAM:

Fig 3.1 architecture diagram

RELATED WORK:

In our project, we leverage computer vision and Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) to enhance rehabilitation monitoring by incorporating dizziness detection and fall prevention. Utilizing cameras to capture real-time video feeds of patients, the data undergo preprocessing to extract relevant information, including human key points and body postures. The system accurately identifies and tracks key body joints, offering rehabilitation professionals valuable insights into patients' range of motion and balance during exercises. Additionally, computer vision algorithms

monitor head movement and gaze, enabling the detection of sudden or abnormal movements indicative of dizziness or instability. Continuous tracking of posture and movement allows the system to identify irregularities that may lead to a fall, issuing warnings for swift preventive measures. Real-time monitoring is a core feature, emphasizing the project's commitment to providing timely insights for improved patient care.

METHODOLOGY:

LIBRARY USED

OPEN CV

OpenCV (Open-Source Computer Vision) is an open-source computer vision and machine learning software library. It was initially developed by Intel Corporation, and now it is maintained by the OpenCV community. The library provides over 2500 optimized algorithms that can be used to detect and recognize faces, identify objects, classify human actions in videos, track camera movements, and more

OpenCV is written in C++, but also provides Python and Java bindings, making it accessible to developers in multiple programming languages. It is widely used in various industries such as automotive, medical, robotics, and security, to name a few.

Some of the key features of OpenCV include object detection, object tracking, face detection, image segmentation, and machine learning algorithms. It also includes several pre-trained models that can be used for various applications. Additionally, it provides a user-friendly interface to visualize and debug image processing algorithms.

OpenCV is a versatile and powerful library that has contributed significantly to the development of computer vision and machine learning applications. Its wide in range of functions and easy-to-use interface make it an essential tool for developers and researchers working in the field of computer vision.

WINSOUND

The `winsound` module in Python is a built-in library designed for Windows operating systems, offering straightforward sound-playing capabilities. It enables developers to interact with the sound system by playing sound files or system sounds without the need for external libraries. Although somewhat limited in features, `winsound` provides a convenient way to incorporate sound into Python applications, supporting various formats such as WAV files and system beeps. This module allows developers to control the frequency and duration of sounds, making it suitable for implementing basic audio notifications or feedback in applications on the Windows platform.

SCIPY

Scipy, a Python scientific computing library, enhances human pose estimation when integrated with OpenCV (cv2). Leveraging Scipy's optimization and mathematical functions, developers can refine pose estimation algorithms, optimize joint position calculations, and boost accuracy in identifying human body keypoints. Its functionality proves particularly valuable for improving precision in applications like motion analysis, fitness tracking, and rehabilitation monitoring. By reducing errors and fine-tuning parameters, Scipy contributes to more accurate and meaningful results in tasks where precise human pose estimation is crucial for generating valuable insights.

DLIB

Dlib, a versatile C++ library, is renowned for its focus on machine learning, computer vision, and image processing. Created by Davis King, it has gained popularity in research and development for its robust tools. Notably effective in facial recognition, object detection, and shape prediction, Dlib serves as a valuable resource in diverse applications.

TECHNOLOGY USED

CNN

Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) are a specialized form of deep neural networks

designed for processing structured grid data, such as images. Comprising convolutional layers, pooling layers, and fully connected layers, CNNs excel in feature extraction and pattern recognition. They automatically learn hierarchical representations of data by applying convolutional filters, enabling effective image classification, object detection, and feature mapping.

CNNs have revolutionized computer vision tasks, demonstrating exceptional performance in image recognition, facial recognition, and medical image analysis. Their ability to capture spatial hierarchies in data makes them a fundamental technology in the field of artificial intelligence and machine learning.

OPEN POSE

OpenPose stands out as a powerful computer vision library for human pose estimation, offering detailed insights into the skeletal structure from images or video. Developed by Carnegie Mellon University researchers, it employs deep learning and CNNs to detect key body joints like wrists and facial features. Notably, Open Pose excels in simultaneously estimating the full-body pose, including hands and fingers, making it widely influential and adopted in diverse applications.

TECHNIQUES USED

MEDIAPIPE

Media pipe is an open-source framework developed by Google that offers a comprehensive solution for building real-time multimodal perceptual pipelines. Designed for applications in computer vision, machine learning, and signal processing, Media pipe provides a library of pre-built components and tools for tasks such as hand tracking, pose estimation, face detection, and more. Its modular architecture allows developers to create custom pipelines easily.

With cross-platform support, it empowers the development of diverse applications,

from augmented reality and gesture recognition to healthcare and robotics, making it a versatile and accessible tool for projects requiring complex perception tasks.

CMAKE

CMake is an open-source cross-platform build system widely used in software development. Serving as a meta-build system, CMake generates native build files (e.g., Makefiles, Visual Studio projects) based on a unified configuration. Developers define build processes in CMakeLists.txt files, allowing for platform-independent project management.

Its versatility accommodates diverse languages and facilitates the creation of efficient, consistent, and scalable build environments. With an emphasis on simplicity and extensibility, CMake streamlines the compilation process, enabling seamless collaboration across different operating systems and build tools. Its adoption is prevalent in projects ranging from small-scale applications to large-scale software development endeavors.

MODULES

- a. Make Detection & Draw Keypoints
- b. Rehabilitation Monitoring
- c. Drowsiness Detection
- d. Fall Detection & Prevention

MODULES DESCRIPTION

a) MAKE DETECTION & DRAW KEYPOINTS

This stage involves leveraging computer vision, particularly Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), for precise keypoint detection in identifying major body joints, like the head, shoulders, and knees. Using datasets like COCO and tools such as Media Pipe, this process transforms raw data into visually interpretable representations. Accuracy in keypoint detection is crucial, forming the basis for subsequent analysis.

Media Pipe further aids by drawing key points on patient images, providing healthcare professionals with an intuitive understanding of movements. COCO's comprehensive dataset proves invaluable for training, and Media Pipe's real-time pose estimation simplifies rendering, facilitating deeper insights into patients' conditions and supporting informed decision-making in healthcare.

The accuracy of this keypoint detection is paramount, as it forms the foundation for subsequent analysis and tracking. Once the key body joints are detected, Media Pipe, a powerful tool for real-time pose estimation, can be employed to draw key points on the patient's silhouette or image. MediaPipe simplifies the process by providing pre-trained models for pose estimation and rendering, transforming raw data into a visually interpretable format.

Fig 8.1 Make Detection & Draw Keypoints

b) REHABILITATION MONITORING

In this module Rehabilitation monitoring emerges as a crucial application empowering healthcare professional to meticulously track patients' movements throughout therapy sessions.

This module, through precise detection and analysis of key body joints and postures, offers invaluable insights into a patient's progress. The capability to accurately assess improvements enables therapists to tailor rehabilitation programs, ensuring adherence to prescribed exercises. Real-time feedback and monitoring play an instrumental role in

elevating the overall effectiveness of rehabilitation efforts, ultimately contributing to more successful outcomes for patients in their recovery from injuries .

Fig 8.2 Rehabilitation Monitoring

c) DROWSINESS DETECTION

In this drowsiness detection module in human pose estimation through computer vision is a pivotal aspect of physiological monitoring. Analyzing both head and body movements, this module identifies irregular or unstable postures indicative of dizziness or balance issues. Real-time assessment facilitates immediate intervention, ensuring patient safety.

This technology holds significant applications in healthcare, particularly for the timely detection of dizziness episodes, crucial for at-risk individuals, such as the elderly. The system's ability to provide early warnings contributes to accident prevention and addresses potential health concerns, underlining its importance in enhancing patient well-being through proactive monitoring and intervention. This may very useful to the patients in the health considerations and improve their wealthy lifestyle.

d) FALL DETECTION&PREVENTION

In this module, the Fall detection and prevention, seamlessly integrated into human pose estimation using computer vision for patient movement tracking in physiology, assume a pivotal role in healthcare and safety. This sophisticated module performs continuous analysis of patients' postures and movements, promptly identifying falls or abrupt changes in body orientation.

By swiftly responding to fall events, this technology not only enhances patient well-being but also significantly reduces the risk of severe consequences associated with falls. The real-time monitoring capability allows for immediate intervention, ensuring that healthcare professionals can respond promptly to mitigate potential injuries.

This comprehensive approach contributes to a safer healthcare environment, particularly beneficial for elderly or vulnerable individuals, emphasizing the importance of technology in proactively safeguarding patient health and minimizing the impact of unexpected events in the context of rehabilitation and physiological monitoring. This may very useful to the patients in the health considerations and protect them from the major injuries. Further it can be used in various applications to improve the promote the safe of the humans

EXPERIMENTAL RESULT & DISCUSSION

Fig 9.1 Exercise Monitoring -Correct Posture

Fig 9.2 Exercise Monitoring - Incorrect Posture

CONCLUSION

Human pose estimation through computer vision has become a transformative tool in the realm of rehabilitation monitoring, with a pronounced emphasis on dizziness detection and fall prevention. These issues significantly impact the elderly and those recuperating from diverse medical conditions.

Fig 9.3 Drowsiness Detected

Fig 9.4 Fall Detection & Prevention

The technology's non-invasive and cost-effective nature enables healthcare professionals to monitor critical factors like balance, gait, and posture, thereby reducing the risk of falls and minimizing dizziness. A key advantage lies in its continuous and real-time assessment capabilities, offering a comprehensive view of a patient's progress compared to traditional periodic assessments.

The versatility of computer vision allows for implementation in various healthcare settings, from clinical environments to home-based rehabilitation programs, rendering it an adaptable and promising solution.

Dizziness detection and fall prevention constitute integral aspects of this research, with computer vision algorithms analyzing individual movements and postures to identify irregularities and patterns associated with dizziness. This enables early intervention to prevent more severe health problems.

The technology's fall detection capability is equally crucial, swiftly identifying falls and alerting caregivers or emergency services, significantly reducing response time.

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